

Nontarget and suspect screening reveals the presence of multiple plastic-related compounds in polar bear, killer whale, narwhal and long-finned pilot whale blubber from East Greenland[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The monitoring of legacy contaminants in sentinel northern marine mammals has revealed some of the highest concentrations globally. However, investigations into the presence of chemicals of emerging Arctic concern (CEACs) and other lesser-known chemicals are rarely conducted, if at all. Here, we used a nontarget/suspect approach to screen for thousands of different chemicals, including many CEACs and plastic-related compounds (PRCs) in blubber/adipose from killer whales (*Orcinus orca*), narwhals (*Monodon monoceros*), long-finned pilot whales (*Globicephala melas*), and polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) in East Greenland. 138 compounds were tentatively identified mostly as PRCs, and four were confirmed using authentic standards: di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), diethyl phthalate (DEP), di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate (DPPHP), and one antioxidant (Irganox 1010). Three other PRCs, a nonylphenol isomer, 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol, and dioctyl sebacate, exhibited fragmentation patterns matching those in library databases. While phthalates were only above detection limits in some polar bear and narwhal, Irganox 1010, nonylphenol, and 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol were detected in >50% of all samples. This study represents the first application of a nontarget/suspect screening approach in Arctic cetaceans, leading to the identification of multiple PRCs in their blubber. Further nontarget analyses are warranted to comprehensively characterize the extent of CEAC and PRC contamination within Arctic marine food webs.

1. Introduction

Marine mammals in the Arctic, including polar bear (*Ursus maritimus*) and toothed whales (*Odontocetes*), are considered sentinels for assessing exposures and effects of contaminants in the Arctic (Dietz et al., 2019; Borgå et al., 2022). As some populations of these species show among the highest concentrations globally of many “known” legacy contaminants (McKinney et al., 2011a; Desforges et al., 2018; Letcher et al., 2018; Dietz et al., 2019), they are routinely monitored for persistent organic pollutant (POPs) using targeted screening approaches (Dietz et al., 2013; Desforges et al., 2018; Dietz et al., 2019). Routine monitoring employs established methods to identify and quantify a suite

of targeted compounds using authentic analytical standards (de Boer et al., 2022). Although this approach has produced accurate and reproducible results for decades, it has historically been limited to (semi-)volatile compounds including legacy contaminants (e.g., polychlorinated biphenyls [PCBs] and dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethanes [DDTs]; Vinaixa et al., 2016). In addition, molecular ions are commonly absent or of low intensity in targeted gas chromatography mass spectrometry with electron ionization (GC-EI-MS), making molecular formula determination of unknown compounds challenging (Furey et al., 2013; Hollender et al., 2017). As such, unknown (or unexpected) compounds, including new/emerging contaminants, are inevitably missed by targeted screening approaches (Hollender et al., 2017).

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With many target-screened contaminants already banned/regulated nationally and globally by the Stockholm Convention, new replacement chemicals are being produced, and many of these in high production (Goldenman, 2017), defined as high production volume (HPV) chemicals (OECD, 2023). Some of these current-use chemicals have been detected in the Arctic; however, for many, their bioaccumulation, biomagnification, and toxicity in marine mammals is largely unknown (Sonne et al., 2021). Multiple recent studies have detailed comprehensive assessments of new/emerging chemicals that have a high potential reach the Arctic and accumulate in marine food webs (AMAP, 2016; Muir et al., 2019; Gibson, 2020). Muir et al. (2019) listed ~3500 potentially persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic chemicals, some of which included HPV chemicals, with a potential for long-range transport to the Arctic. A subset of compounds from this list, those with the highest toxic, bioaccumulative, and long-range transport potential (i.e., “POP-like” potential) were designated as chemicals of emerging Arctic concern (CEACs; Muir et al., 2019; AMAP, 2020). International and national monitoring programs including the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program (AMAP) and Canada’s Northern Contaminants Program (NCP) have also compiled comprehensive assessments of CEACs detected in Arctic seawater and air including organophosphate flame retardants, paraffins, siloxanes, and plastics/plastic-related compounds (PRCs), such as phthalates, antioxidants, UV stabilizers, and micro/nanoplastics (AMAP, 2020; NCP, 2024). As marine mammals in the Arctic often occupy high trophic positions, are long-lived, and possess large quantities of fatty storage tissues (Borgå et al., 2004), bioaccumulation of CEACs and/or mixtures of them is possible, but largely unknown (Sonne et al., 2021).

To identify new CEACs in marine mammal tissues, a newer approach, nontarget screening, may be useful. In the absence of authentic standards, nontarget approaches can identify and semi-quantify a wide range of “unknown” chemical compounds (Díaz et al., 2012; Pieke et al., 2018; Manz et al., 2023). A subcategory of nontarget screening, suspect screening, involves the automated detection of compounds in comparison to the mass spectra of compound libraries (Krauss et al., 2010; Díaz et al., 2012). As true nontarget analysis involves the detection of compounds without any suspect compound information or database, suspect screening is typically used to tentatively identify compounds of potential interest (Hollender et al., 2017; Manz et al., 2023). Although no routine nontarget/suspect approach exists for the analysis of contaminants in marine mammal blubber, chromatography coupled to high resolution MS (HRMS) has been increasingly popular in the nontarget/suspect analyses of emerging contaminants in a wide variety of challenging environmental matrixes, including some biological tissues (Schymanski et al., 2015; Hollender et al., 2017; Von Eyken and Bayen, 2019; Tian et al., 2020b). In particular, using quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) HRMS in nontarget analysis has been shown to provide high mass accuracy for the formula generation and high confidence in structure prediction (Knolhoff and Croley, 2016; Knolhoff et al., 2016).

Nontarget/suspect approaches have rarely been used in any Arctic marine mammal species, despite calls by international monitoring programs such as AMAP for the development of nontarget approaches to aid in identification of potential chemicals of concern (AMAP, 2016). In fact, for most sub-Arctic or Arctic toothed whales, including killer whale (*Orcinus orca*), narwhal (*Monodon monoceros*), and long-finned pilot whale (*Globicephala melas*), a nontarget/suspect screening approach to identify any “unknown” or predicted contaminants of concern, including most AMAP-identified CEACs, has not been reported. Similarly, only two studies to date have used a nontarget/suspect approach in polar bear, identifying some emerging halogenated organics and PRCs in adipose and liver samples (Routti et al., 2016) and per- and poly-fluorinated compounds (PFAS) in liver (Chu and Letcher, 2024). Instead, nearly all nontarget/suspect screening studies in the subarctic and Arctic to date have been conducted in other environmental media, largely marine and freshwaters, sediments, soil, air, and some lower trophic level consumers, including mussels and some fishes (González-Gaya

et al., 2021). These studies in other environmental media/biota are likely not comparable to marine mammals, which may show far higher levels of CEACs based on well-documented high concentrations of legacy POPs (Dietz et al., 2019). As such, as several other “unknown” and potentially toxic compounds may also be present, the implementation of a nontarget approach to identify never-before-screened chemicals, which may include CEACs, in marine mammal sentinels is warranted.

Here, we apply nontarget and suspect screening approaches to 1) screen for “unknown” environmental contaminants, 2) confirm contaminant presence using authentic standards, 3) use semi-quantitative approaches to estimate concentrations of a subset of these confirmed compounds, and 4) compare levels of confirmed compounds to legacy contaminants in the same samples of blubber/adipose in multiple marine mammal species sampled in East Greenland, including polar bear and narwhal and northward-range expanding killer whale and pilot whale. To date, this study is the first to implement a nontarget/suspect workflow to investigate unknown contaminant presence in any cetacean in the Arctic, to our knowledge.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample collection

A subset of the samples used in Pedersen et al. (2024), which analyzed these same four species for PCBs and DDTs, were included in the current study. In short, 15 killer whale in 2012–2014 (n = 13) and 2021 (n = 2), 15 narwhal in 2015, 15 long-finned pilot whale in 2021, and 15 polar bear in 2021 (Table S1) were opportunistically collected during subsistence harvests by local hunters from East Greenland communities in Ittoqqortoormiit, Tasiilaq and Kulusuk (Table 1; Fig. S1). Full-blubber depth samples collected from each whale and subcutaneous adipose from polar bear were stored at –20 °C until they arrived at McGill University, where they were then stored at –80 °C until time of analysis. Further information on age class and sex determination is available in Pedersen et al. (2024).

2.2. Sample extraction

All samples were extracted using a modified QuEChERS (quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged and safe) method that we previously developed (Pedersen et al., 2023) and all contaminant extraction information was

Table 1

Sampling location and GPS coordinates, years of collection, and sample size for each location and year for each of blubber/adipose samples (n = 15 per species) from East Greenland.

Species	Year Collected	Sampling Location	GPS Coordinates	Sample Size
Killer whale	2012	Tasiilaq, Greenland	65°37 N 37°57 W	3
		Tasiilaq, Greenland	65°37 N 37°57 W	3
	2013	Kulusuk, Greenland	65°20 N 37°10 W	2
		Tasiilaq, Greenland	65°37 N 37°57 W	5
	2021	Kulusuk, Greenland	65°20 N 37°10 W	1
		Ittoqqortoormiit, Greenland	70°29 N 21°58 W	1
Narwhal	2015	Gaasefjord, Greenland	70°10 N 27°15 W	15
		Tasiilaq, Greenland	65°37 N 37°57 W	10
Long-finned pilot whale	2021	Tasiilaq, Greenland	65°37 N 37°57 W	10
		Kulusuk, Greenland	65°20 N 37°10 W	5
Polar bear	2021	Ittoqqortoormiit, Greenland	70°29 N 21°58 W	15

described previously (Pedersen et al., 2024). All authentic analytical standards (Table S2; 45 standards) were purchased from Toronto Research Chemicals (Toronto, Canada) or Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). After analysis for legacy PCBs and OC pesticides, GC-MS extracts were reconstituted in methanol by blowing down the original isoctane solvent on a nitrogen evaporator to ~50 μL , adding 200 μL of methanol, and evaporating again to ~50 μL . Extracts were transferred to a new HPLC vial along with 1 mL of 50:50 (v:v) methanol: acetonitrile. The solution was passed through a 3 mL syringe attached to a 0.2 μm filter (Fisher Scientific, Pittsburg, PA, USA) prior to instrument analysis.

2.3. Background contaminant control

To avoid plastic-related contamination during the sample collection and extraction, the use of plastic labware was limited as much as possible. Following collection, large pieces of blubber/adipose (ranging from 25 to 100 g) from all narwhal, polar bear, and killer whale were subset and wrapped in a sheet of acetone-rinsed aluminum foil, while large pilot whale samples (ranging from 115 to 200 g samples) were placed directly in plastic bags, then all samples were shipped to McGill University. Prior to chemical extraction at McGill University, only the innermost portion (0.1 g) was sampled from the innermost portion of each large piece of blubber (i.e., was not touching the foil or plastic) using an acetone-rinsed metal scalpel blade. During the chemical extraction, plastic equipment was limited to the clean-up cartridges (see Pedersen et al., 2023) and filter syringes. All glassware was cleaned with deionized water and solvent rinsed three times, dried, and then solvent rinsed again three times prior to experimentation. As the usage of plastic was unavoidable, one procedural blank was also extracted with each batch of samples (for a total of five) and was processed and analyzed on the instrument the same way as blubber/adipose samples. Although field blanks were not taken, contamination from field sampling was previously shown to not be a source of PRCs (i.e., all field blanks showed no PRC contamination; Routti et al., 2021). Although pilot whale samples were placed directly in plastic bags, they did not show a greater number of nontarget or suspect screened compounds (see results sections 3.1 and 3.2). As such, sampling from the innermost layer of blubber is likely sufficient to avoid background PRC contamination from packaging.

2.4. Instrument analysis

Samples were analyzed using a 1290 Infinity II LC from Agilent Technologies (Santa, Clara, USA) coupled to an Agilent 6545 Q-TOF MS, in both positive (ESI⁺) and negative (ESI⁻) electrospray ionization modes. The LC system was equipped with a Poreshell120 EC-C18 analytical column (Agilent Technologies; 2.7 μm \times 3 mm \times 100 mm) fitted with a Poroshell 120 (EC-C18; 2.7 μm \times 3.0 mm \times 5 mm) guard column (Agilent Technologies). The mobile phase consisted of water (solvent A) and methanol/acetonitrile (1:1 vol/vol, solvent B), both containing 5 mM ammonium acetate, at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The percentage of organic mobile phase B increased linearly as follows: initially at 5% for 0.5 min, then increased to 100% from 1 to 8 min, and then maintained at 100% from 8 to 13 min; reduced to 5% from 13 to 13.5 min, held at 5% from 13.5 to 15 min, followed by 1.5 min post run. The injection volume was 10 μL and the column temperature was set to 30 °C. MS conditions were: drying gas temperature = 175 °C, drying gas flow rate = 10 L/min, sheath gas temperature = 375 °C, sheath gas flow rate = 12 L/min, nebulizer pressure = 30 psi, capillary voltage = 4000 V, fragmentor voltage = 125 V, skimmer voltage = 50 V, and nozzle

voltage = 1000 V (ESI⁺) or at 2000 V (ESI⁻). Full scan MS data were recorded at a mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) range from 100 to 1700 with a scan rate of 2 spectra/sec and were collected using both centroid and profile modes. Targeted MS/MS data for features of interest and analytical standards was collected with three different collision energies in succession (10, 20, and 40 V). Two reference ions (m/z at 121.0508 and 922.0098 for ESI⁺, 112.9856 and 1033.9881 for ESI⁻) were used in each ion mode for automatic mass recalibration during data acquisition. For the targeted compounds, target m/z and retention times are available (Table S3).

2.5. Quality assurance/quality control

As pooled quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) samples are essential when conducting nontarget analysis (Gika et al., 2014), one pooled QC sample was prepared by mixing 10 μL of each sample. The pooled QC sample was analyzed every 20 marine mammal samples (5 times total) to control for instrument background noise, mass measurement reproducibility, and retention time drifts.

2.6. Nontarget screening, suspect screening, and data filtering

Nontarget analysis of MS-full scan data was performed using the software MassHunter Profinder B.10.00 from Agilent Technologies. Molecular features in all data including blanks and pooled QC samples were first extracted by the “Batch Recursive Feature Extraction” algorithm (RT tolerance \pm 0.15 min, mass tolerance \pm 20 ppm, absolute height threshold \geq 5000 counts, score \geq 70). The total molecular features extracted in each ion mode were filtered based on following criteria: detection frequency of features in the five pooled QC data \geq 40%, and relative standard deviation (RSD%) of features' abundance in the five pooled QC data $<$ 40%. Hierarchical clustering analysis with Euclidean distances were performed on the filtered molecular features to explore groupings within the dataset using Mass Profiler Professional 15.1 (MPP, Agilent Technologies).

Suspect screening was also conducted on the same dataset in “Batch Targeted Feature Extraction” mode (RT tolerance \pm 0.05 min, mass tolerance \pm 20 ppm, absolute height threshold \geq 5000 counts), and the resulting MS information was screened against the *Extractables & Leachables PCDL* (Personal Compound Database and Library; Agilent Technologies). This database was selected as it contains many CEAC groups including PFAS, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), antioxidants, UV stabilizers, phthalates, plasticizers, and many others; however, we also personalized this database with the addition of another $>$ 100 compounds that are likely CEACs from *AMAP 2016 and 2020 assessments* (Table S4). The minimum total score for the identification of a compound was set to 80%. The total score indicates the probability that the feature is the actual compound in the matching library (i.e. a score of 100% is a perfect match) and is based on: an isotope abundance score, an isotope spacing score and a mass match score (Knolhoff et al., 2016a). A list of possible compound candidates was generated and further sequentially filtered using the same QC data filters as the nontarget screening, but the following filters were added: maximum peak area of each feature $>$ mean plus 3 times of standard deviation of signals in procedural blanks; maximum peak area of each feature $>$ 100,000. Targeted MS/MS spectra of features of interest were compared either with PCDL MS/MS spectra library or subjected to SIRIUS for structure prediction (Schymanski et al., 2015; Dührkop et al., 2019; Schmid et al., 2023). 45 authentic standards (Table S2) were used to confirm the tentatively identified molecular features based on the

retention time and targeted MS/MS fragment patterns.

Compound identification confidence was also based on Schymanski et al. (2014), where Level 3 indicates a tentative candidate (but insufficient evidence for one exact structure), Level 2 indicates a probable structure (from literature or library spectrum match from MS and MS/MS), and Level 1 indicates a confirmed structure via an appropriate reference standard (with matching less than 0.1 min difference in retention time and matching targeted MS/MS fragmentation patterns).

2.7. Semi-quantification of select compounds

A subset of identified and confirmed compounds were semi-quantified; however, this was only done for compounds with an available mass-labelled authentic standard (Table S2), which were unavailable for many of the tentatively identified compounds. To determine percent recovery (calculated as [peak area in sample/peak area in standard] *100), we spiked three blubber samples with the mass-labelled standard mix (mix 5) prior to the QuEChERS extraction, then injected them on the LC-QTOF post-extraction. Limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) were calculated as the average concentration of the compound in the procedural blanks plus three and ten times of the standard deviation, respectively.

2.8. Comparisons to legacy contaminants

For a subset of confirmed compounds, we compared peak areas (divided by starting material weight, i.e. ~0.1 g) to concentrations (in wet weight) of the recalcitrant legacy contaminant, PCB-153 (Pedersen et al., 2024), using linear correlations as a preliminary indication of biomagnification. As PCB-153 is highly biomagnifying and increases with trophic position in food webs (and previously shown to be higher in likely marine mammal-feeding polar bear and killer whale relative to fish/squid feeding narwhal and pilot whale; Pedersen et al., 2024), significant and positive correlations likely suggest similar characteristics for the nontarget screened compound to PCB-153. Furthermore, information regarding toxicity and “POP-like” potential for all confirmed and tentatively identified PRCs was available and compiled from the

PlastChem Database on the State of the Science on Plastic Chemicals (Wagner et al., 2024). All mg/kg concentrations and peak areas were log (x+1) transformed, and all data achieved normality.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. QA/QC and clustering analysis

Mean recovery for the 11 mass-labelled standard mix was $63.9 \pm 18.1\%$ (Table S5) from matrix-spiked samples, demonstrating sufficient analyte recovery. The mean mass accuracies for all mass labelled standards were acceptable, with a mean accuracy of 0.86 ± 0.24 ppm (Table S5). Peak areas of mass-labelled standards post-spiked in sample matrix were similar to the corresponding value of standard in pure solvent at the same concentration level, indicating no significant matrix effects. Thus, the concentration of confirmed PRCs were semi-quantified via one-point calibration (see Equation 1 in Supporting Information). Contamination of a few PRCs was also evident in procedural blanks, and as such, concentrations in the samples were also corrected for the presence of each respective compound found in the procedural blanks.

To ensure the repeatability/reproducibility of the analysis, we verified the position of the pooled QA/QC injections in the hierarchical clustering analysis from the filtered features from nontarget screening (Fig. 1), suspect screening (Figs. S2 and S3), and from the PCA (Fig. S4). From the nontarget and suspect screenings, QA/QC injections in each analysis were grouped together, indicating the analysis was repeatable and could be included in the next steps for data treatment (Sangster et al., 2006).

Both the nontarget and suspect screening clustering analyses also indicates distinct groupings based on species in both ESI⁺ and ESI⁻, suggesting interspecific differences in nontarget screened chemical profiles. However, as some individuals in each species cluster outside of their respective groupings, other factors, such as differences in sex/age class (i.e. adult male, adult female, and subadult), may also impact individual chemical profiles. In particular, adult males tended to cluster outside of their species groupings. For example, two male polar bear (in ESI⁺) and two male killer whale (in ESI⁺) clustered separately from

Fig. 1. Hierarchical clustering analysis (A) in ESI⁺ and (B) ESI⁻ mode by LC-QTOF-MS based on the peak areas from all nontarget screening features in individual marine mammal blubber samples.

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the feature filtering steps (from both ESI⁺ and ESI⁻) from 1) the total initial features (outermost circle) from nontarget screening, 2) tentative matching features to personalized library database with matching score of >80% from suspect screening, 3) filtering from pooled quality assurance/quality controls injections and 4) filtering by compounds above the mean + 3 σ of the blanks (innermost circle).

adult females and subadults (Fig. S3). Although trends vary based on legacy contaminant, the more recalcitrant PCBs (e.g., CB-153, 180) tended to show higher concentrations in adult males and subadults relative to adult females (Pedersen et al., 2024). In general, adult male marine mammals tend to show increasing concentrations of POPs with age due to a lack of capacity to offload burdens to young that females have through gestation and particularly lactation (Pedro et al., 2017; Dietz et al., 2019). As such, the particular feature groupings, with some adult males showing distinct patterns from adult females, could suggest some features behave similar to known POPs in terms of bioaccumulation in males and offloading of burdens in females to offspring. However, as patterns are not entirely discernible among all individuals when comparing across age class/sex groupings, other factors still likely influence differences in individual chemical profiles, such as diet, body condition, migration, seasonality, year of collection, and lipid content.

3.2. Data filtering

From the nontarget screening approach, 10,927 unique molecular features were obtained from both ESI⁺ (6115 features) and ESI⁻ (4825 features) for all 60 blubber samples (Fig. 2). From the suspect screening, 1830 features (972 in ESI⁺ and 856 in ESI⁻) were tentatively identified with a matching score of >80% in the library database. Of these features, most (~83%) were simultaneously detected in ~20% of individuals above the mean + 3 σ of the blanks (Fig. S5). The mean number of features above the mean + 3 σ of the blanks also varied significantly by species with: narwhal (83 features) = pilot whale (79) > killer whale (74) = polar bear (70) (Fig. S5).

From the suspect screening approach, filtering from the tentative matching features from the pooled QA/QC injections yielded 698

features (240 in ESI⁺ and 458 in ESI⁻). Out of these compounds, 138 (86 in ESI⁺ and 52 in ESI⁻) were above the mean + 3 σ of the blanks (see Table S6 for full list of compounds). This number of suspect-screened features is similar to those reported elsewhere, including in water samples from an urban estuary (205 features; Tian et al., 2020a), Arctic marine zooplankton (127 features; Sørensen et al., 2023), and bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*) blubber from Brazil (158 features; Alonso et al., 2017).

Although this subset of 138 compounds details a comprehensive list of CEACs in Arctic marine mammal blubber/adipose, including some phthalates and their metabolites (e.g., di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate [DEHP] and mono-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate [MEHP]), pesticides (e.g., Triclosan), fluorinated compounds (e.g., perfluorohexanesulfonic acid), UV stabilizers (e.g., UV-320, and Irgacure 369), antioxidants (e.g., Ethanox 702, Irganox 1010), synthetic dyes (e.g., Sudan III, Malachite Green), and surfactants (Surfynol 104), these compounds are only a tentative confirmation of the respective compounds, equated to a confidence Level 4 on the Schymanski et al. (2014) scale. As the confirmation of 138 compounds across 60 blubber samples would be prohibitively costly and time-consuming, a subset of this list was instead identified based on available standards (i.e., for Level 1 confidence), as detailed in Sections 3.3 to 3.6.

3.3. Phthalates

Features at m/z 223.0971 ([M+H]⁺, 8.21 min), 391.2848 ([M+H]⁺, 11.79 min), and 447.3482 ([M+H]⁺, 14.08 min) were identified in the library as diethyl phthalate (DEP), di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), and di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate (DPHP). The identification for all three compounds was confirmed (i.e. identification confidence Level 1; Schymanski et al., 2014) with a retention time match of less than 0.1 min difference and MS/MS fragmentation patterns match relative to the available authentic standards (Table 2, Fig. S6).

Several other features were tentatively identified as phthalates, including dibutyl phthalate, benzyl butyl phthalate, and dibenzyl phthalate, respectively. These compounds showed a retention time match with available standards, but MS/MS spectra in samples was of low quality (i.e., very small peaks), likely from relatively small signals from parent ions, preventing further confirmation (see Table S7).

For phthalates with level 1 identification confirmation (i.e., DEP, DEHP, DPHP), detection frequencies (calculated as the number of samples above the blank mean + 3 σ /15 *100) of these compounds varied widely by species (Table 3). DEP was detected in 20% of polar bear (3/15 individuals), DEHP was detected in 20% (3/15 individuals) of polar bear and 13% (2/15 individuals) of narwhal, while DPHP was only detected in the same two narwhal. DEP, DEHP, and DPHP were not detected in any killer whale or pilot whale. Correlations of phthalate peak areas/starting material weight with concentrations of legacy contaminants (PCB-153 in wet weight) in the same individuals showed no significant correlation for DEP and DEHP ($R^2 = 0.01$ and $R^2 = 0.02$, respectively), but a significant and negative correlation for DPHP ($R^2 = 0.21$ and $p < 0.01$; Fig. S7). These models likely suggest limited or no biomagnification potential of these phthalates (as supported elsewhere; Gobas et al., 2003; Mackintosh et al., 2004; Lynch et al., 2022), and even potential trophic dilution (as seen in DPHP; Fig. S7), also supported elsewhere in both aquatic (Gobas et al., 2003) and terrestrial (McLachlan, 1996; Franco et al., 2007) food webs.

For semi-quantified phthalate concentrations (i.e. DEP and DEHP, based on available mass-labelled standards), DEP concentrations ranged

Table 2
Nontarget identification of select plastic-related compounds with high identification confidence in marine mammal blubber/adipose.

Feature m/z	RT (min) in standard	Molecular formula	Suspected ID from library	RT match from standard	MS/MS match from standard	MS/MS match from library	Identification confidence ^a
ESI ⁺							
223.0971	8.210	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	Diethyl phthalate (DEP)	Yes	Yes	NA	1
391.2848	11.792	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	Di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP)	Yes	Yes	NA	1
447.3482	14.079	C ₃₈ H ₄₆ O ₄	Di (2-propylheptyl) phthalate (DPPHP)	Yes	Yes	NA	1
1194.8160	13.253	C ₇₃ H ₁₀₈ O ₁₂	Irganox 1010	Yes	Yes	NA	1
ESI ⁻							
205.1603	9.78 ^b	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	2,6-Di- <i>tert</i> -Butylphenol	NA	NA	Yes ^c	2
219.1758	10.16 ^b	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	Nonylphenol (or isomers)	NA	NA	Yes ^c	3
427.3777	14.25 ^b	C ₃₆ H ₅₆ O ₄	Dioctyl sebacate (or isomers)	NA	NA	Yes ^c	3
498.9299	8.668	C ₈ HF ₁₇ O ₃ S	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	Yes	Yes	NA	1

^a From Schymanski et al. (2014).

^b Average retention time in samples, since no standard was available.

^c SIRIUS score >85.

from <0.14–0.25 mg/kg wet weight (ww), but DEHP ranged slightly higher from <0.54–7.29 mg/kg ww in all blubber/adipose samples (Table 4). Phthalate concentrations were relatively high in blanks, likely from contamination during chemical extraction, as DEP and DEHP can migrate from plastic (e.g., plastic tubing, cartridges, syringes, etc.) to surrounding materials (García Ibarra et al., 2018; Rastkari et al., 2018); due to blank subtraction, this led to high limits of detection, which are similar to those reported previously (Fankhauser-Noti and Grob, 2007; Routti et al., 2021).

Phthalates are AMAP-classified CEACs and many are considered HPV PRCs (AMAP, 2016; AMAP, 2020). DEHP, in particular, has received intensive scientific interest as a likely endocrine disrupting chemical by the World Health Organization and United Nations Environmental Program (WHO/UNEP, 2013). As such, many phthalates, including DEHP have been globally identified as substances of high concern with regional bans/restrictions, mostly in cosmetics, children's toys, and childcare products (CEPA, 1999; ECHA, 2015; Wang and Qian, 2021). More recently, DEP has been also been classified as a highly hazardous compound due to its reproductive and specific target organ toxicity, although no current global regulation exists (Wagner et al., 2024). Information on DPHP toxicity is more limited, although a potential for endocrine disruption has been reported (Wagner et al., 2024).

Targeted screening studies have previously identified both DEHP and DEP across the Arctic in air, water, sediment, and some biota (Vorkamp et al., 2004; Schlabach et al., 2009; Remberger et al., 2013; Routti et al., 2021). Similar to our findings, DEHP was the most abundant phthalate detected in Norwegian polar bear adipose and cetacean blubber (ranging from <0.012–0.39 mg/kg ww; Routti et al., 2021) and polar bear liver from Greenland (0.13–0.15 mg/kg ww; Vorkamp et al., 2004). Our detection frequencies and limits of detection in polar bear adipose are comparable to those reported elsewhere (8.3% and 0.1 mg/kg ww, respectively; Routti et al., 2021). DEP was similarly detected at lower concentrations (0.016–0.024 mg/kg ww) relative to DEHP in Greenlandic polar bear liver (Vorkamp et al., 2004), although our reported concentrations in adipose were substantially higher. In Norwegian cetaceans, all DEP concentrations in cetacean blubber were similarly below detection limits, although our detection in polar bears was higher (i.e., not detected in Routti et al., 2021 compared to 20% in the present study). However, the present study is the first to confirm the presence of phthalates (DEP and DPHP) in any narwhal, to our knowledge, albeit at low detection frequencies.

The sources and pathways of phthalates to marine mammal blubber/adipose are not fully known. However, high concentrations of phthalates, most notably DEHP, have been identified in high Arctic seawater, with an estimated 30 and 190 tons per year atmospherically deposited to the Greenland Sea and Arctic Ocean, respectively (Xie et al., 2007). Following deposition to surface waters, phthalate ingestion has been shown to occur in plankton, yet studies suggest limited biomagnification potential of phthalates to top predators (Mackintosh et al., 2004; Kim et al., 2016). Instead, trophic dilution of phthalate diesters and their monoester metabolites has been reported, suggesting further metabolic breakdown/and or rapid excretion in high trophic level marine organisms (Hu et al., 2016). No phthalate metabolites were identified in the current study, further suggesting high xenobiotic biotransformation potential across all studied species, although extraction-based losses of these more hydrophilic metabolites may also be likely. As such, given low detection frequency across all species, and a likely limited biomagnification potential, phthalate bioaccumulation, at least for DEP, DEHP, and DPHP, to top predator marine mammals in the Arctic is likely relatively low, especially compared to known concentrations of legacy contaminants.

3.4. Antioxidants

The feature at m/z 1194.8160 ($[M+Na]^+$, 13.25 min) was identified in the library as Irganox 1010. The identification was confirmed at

Table 3

Detection frequencies in % (ND = nondetected) of all plastic-related compounds with high identification confidence (level 1, 2, or 3) in blubber/adipose samples.

Compound name	Detection Frequency (%)*			
	Killer whale	Narwhal	Pilot whale	Polar bear
Phthalates				
Diethyl phthalate (DEP)	ND	ND	ND	20
Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP)	ND	13	ND	20
Di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate (DHP)	ND	13	ND	ND
Antioxidant				
Irganox 1010	67	80	ND	13
Alkyl Phenols				
2,6-di- <i>tert</i> -butylphenol	40	27	53	67
Nonylphenol isomer	80	80	7	33
Misc. Compounds				
Dioctyl sebacate (or isomers)	27	33	13	7
Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	ND	13	ND	20

*darker colors indicate higher detection frequencies

Table 4

Semi-quantified concentrations (mg/kg wet weight) of phthalates (based on available mass-labelled standard) in blubber/adipose sample.

Feature m/z	Killer whale	Narwhal	Pilot whale	Polar bear
Diethyl phthalate (DEP)	<0.14	<0.14	<0.14	<0.14–0.25 ^a
Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP)	<0.54	<0.54–1.83	<0.54	<0.54–7.29

^a Ranges from samples below detection limits to samples above detection limits.

confidence Level 1 (Table 2, Fig. S8). Another antioxidant was detected at m/z 357.1894 ([M+H]⁺, 10.69 min) and was tentatively identified as Irganox 1081. However, although the retention time in samples matched the available standard, peak areas were too low (mean ~1000) in pooled QA/QC injections and thus did not meet QA/QC criterion (see section 2.6).

Detection frequencies for Irganox 1010 were highest in killer whale (67%) and narwhal (80%), lower in polar bear (13%), and not detected in pilot whale (Table 3). As mass-labelled standards were not available and were not extracted with samples in the method procedure, concentrations were not quantified. Linear correlations comparing Irganox 1010 to PCB-153 in the same individuals were not significant ($R^2 = 0.03$; Fig. S7).

Irganox 1010, a high molecular weight HPV chemical, is a plastic additive used in most polyolefins such as polyethylene, polypropylene, and polybutene (OECD, 2005). Despite its widespread global usage, information on its environmental presence is currently severely lacking (Wagner et al., 2024). High concentrations of Irganox 1010 (up to 1600 µg/g) have been reported in plastic debris and new plastic products (Rani et al., 2017). Although Irganox 1010 has not yet been classified as a CEAC, plastics (i.e. micro- and nanoplastics) and plastic additives (e.g., phthalates) are classified as CEACs (AMAP, 2016; AMAP, 2020), especially as widespread observations of plastic pollution have been observed across the Arctic (Bergmann et al., 2022) and in East Greenland (Morgana et al., 2018). Nonetheless, the present study is the first to identify Irganox 1010 in any marine wildlife tissue, to our knowledge, although similar antioxidant compounds have been detected in seawater (Suhroff and Scholz-Böttcher, 2016).

Ingestion of plastic debris has been suggested as a source of exposure to plastic additives in marine mammals (Fossi et al., 2016; Bainsi et al., 2017; Routti et al., 2021). In Northeast Greenland, plastic ingestion by Arctic fishes, harp seals (*Pagophilus groenlandicus*), and hooded seals (*Cystophora cristata*) has been recently observed (Morgana et al., 2018;

Pinzone et al., 2021), with evidence of polyethylene, polypropylene, and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) accumulation in gastrointestinal (GI) tracts and livers. As Irganox 1010 is one of the most common additives in polyethylene- and polypropylene-based plastics (Hahladakis et al., 2018), subsequent assimilation into marine mammal tissue post-ingestion may be possible, yet the extent to which sorbed additives can transfer from plastics to animal tissues is currently uncertain. However, Irganox 1010 has been shown to significantly migrate from plastic into fatty/oily substrates in a laboratory setting (Marcato et al., 2003). Direct consumption of Irganox 1010 from seawater (i.e., after leeching from plastic) is also unlikely due to its hydrophobicity and high octanol-water partitioning coefficient (19.06; Lynch et al., 2022), although some sorbed additives may accumulate in lower trophic organisms such as plankton (Xin et al., 2023). Direct plastic ingestion has also been shown to be a negligible source of some PRCs (e.g., phthalates) compared to dietary intake (Bakir et al., 2016), suggesting potential accumulation from trophic transfer. However, biomagnification potential is not likely (Fig. S7); given nonsignificant correlations with PCB-153 as biomagnification of large size plastic additives is generally limited (Miller et al., 2020), although it has not yet been investigated for any Irganox antioxidants in any other studies, to our knowledge.

Given the high detection frequencies of Irganox 1010 in the present study, further investigation into the sources, transfer, and toxicity of antioxidants to marine mammal predators is warranted. Differences in feeding habitat and individual diet may impact plastic ingestion as indicated elsewhere (Hahladakis et al., 2018; Pinzone et al., 2021), which may explain our reported interspecific differences in detection frequencies. Toxicity is expected to be low, with high LD₅₀ observed in *Daphnia magna* (86 mg/L) and other animals (USFDA, 2019); although, a recent study indicated decreased growth and survival in Irganox 1010-exposed sea urchins (*Echinus* sp.; Shore et al., 2022). However, targeted analyses are required to confirm the presence of Irganox 1010 and better assess whether the concentrations exceed expected nontoxic thresholds.

3.5. Alkylphenols

Features at m/z 219.1758 ([M-H]⁻, 10.16 min) and 205.1603 ([M-H]⁻, 9.78 min) were initially identified by the library as 4-nonylphenol and 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol, respectively (Table 2). However, the MS/MS fragmentation and retention time of an available 4-nonylphenol standard did not match with samples (Table S7). A branched nonylphenol standard, 4-(1-ethyl-1-methylhexyl)phenol, was also tested and matched retention time, but with a different fragmentation abundance pattern. Instead, SIRIUS predicted six nonylphenol isomer

structures with a high degree of confidence (>84% match), and as such, a confidence level of 3 was assigned, as the confirmation of one nonylphenol structure was not possible. For the other feature 205.1603 ([M-H]⁻, 9.78 min), targeted MS/MS showed a matched fragmentation pattern as 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol with a 96% matching score from SIRIUS prediction (Fig. S10). Thus, a confidence level of 2 was assigned.

For 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol, detection frequencies were as follows: polar bear (67%) > pilot whale (53%) > killer whale (40%) > narwhal (27%). Patterns differed for the nonylphenol isomer compound, with killer whale (80%) = narwhal (80%) > polar bear (33%) > pilot whale (7%). Linear regressions comparing nonylphenol and 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol peak areas to PCB-153 in the same individuals were also nonsignificant ($R^2 = 0.10$ and $R^2 = 0.01$, respectively; Fig. S7).

2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol and some nonylphenols are degradation products of alkylphenol ethoxylates, commonly used as additives in plastics (commonly PVC and polystyrene), detergents, paints, lubricants, and some pesticides (Sharma et al., 2009). In accordance with our findings, multiple C₈- (like 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol) and C₉-alkylphenols (i.e. nonylphenols) were also detected in polar bear plasma from Svalbard (Simon et al., 2013). More recently, 4-nonylphenol, a known persistent and moderately bioaccumulative endocrine disrupting chemical (Soares et al., 2008), was also identified in polar bear liver samples from Svalbard (Routti et al., 2016) and in killer whale liver from the northeast Pacific (Lee et al., 2023) using targeted approaches. 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol has not yet been identified in any marine mammal species, to our knowledge, yet recent assessments have detailed a high potential for specific target organ toxicity, although limited environmental persistence (Wagner et al., 2024). Confirming alkylphenol presence via a nontarget approach is challenging due to the vast number of octyl- and nonyl-alkylphenol constitutional isomers (e.g., >200 nonylphenol isomers; Guenther et al., 2006), making standard purchases and analyses costly and time intensive. However, future studies should aim to screen for the alkylphenols of the highest concern (i.e. 4-nonylphenol; Guenther et al., 2006), detail concentrations, and to confirm 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol presence in marine mammal blubber/adipose.

3.6. Other compounds of potential concern

The feature at m/z 427.3777 ([M-H]⁻, 14.25 min) in samples was identified in the library as dioctyl sebacate. Detection frequencies were as follows: narwhal (33%) > killer whale (27%) > pilot whale (13%) > polar bear (7%). Standards were not available to confirm this compound. However, based on targeted MS/MS fragmentation patterns, SIRIUS predicted six different confirmations of dioctyl sebacate with matching scores >87%, and as such, a confidence level of 3 was assigned. Dioctyl sebacate and its configurational isomers are PRCs used as plasticizers (Mahrous and Sobhy, 1999), with a potential for toxicity in wildlife (Wagner et al., 2024). However, information of their presence in any environmental compartment is severely lacking (Wagner et al., 2024), and to our knowledge, they have not been reported in any marine wildlife tissues. As such, further investigation using authentic standards is required to confirm its, or its isomers, presence.

The feature at m/z 498.9299 ([M-H]⁻, 8.67 min) was identified in the library as perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) and was confirmed with a retention time match less than 0.1 min difference and MS/MS fragmentation patterns match to the standard (Table 2, see Fig. S11). PFOS was only detected in polar bear (20%) and narwhal (13%). PFOS and other fluorinated compounds have been previously analyzed and detected in killer whale (Gebbinck et al., 2016), narwhal (Carlsson et al., 2014), pilot whale (Dassuncao et al., 2017), and polar bear (Boisvert et al., 2019) liver samples given their proteinophilic nature and accumulate to a far lower degree in fatty tissues (Kelly et al., 2009), likely explaining our lower detection frequencies in blubber/adipose across all individuals. Although our detection frequencies were far lower than those reported elsewhere in polar bear adipose (Boisvert et al., 2019), this is likely a result of extraction-based losses.

Several other compounds of interest are also likely present in these blubber samples but may be missing from the selected library database, concentrated in other tissues (e.g. in muscle or liver), or were not detected due to extraction-based losses. For example, biomagnifying halogenated natural products and metabolites such as hydroxylated and methoxylated polybrominated diphenyl ethers (OH- and MeO-PBDEs) may still be present (Kelly et al., 2008), but were absent in the selected library database. For other chemicals that were included in the library database like bisphenol A (BPA) and tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), mass-labelled BPA spikes carried out through our QuEChERS approach were not detected post-extraction (likely maintained in the aqueous fraction, while the organic fraction was collected). As such, they were likely not detected due to extraction-based losses but may still be present, especially as BPA and TBBPA presence has been documented across the subarctic and Arctic, including in subarctic marine mammal liver (e.g., fin whale, sperm whale, minke whale in South China Sea; Guo et al., 2023), in other Arctic biota (fishes and mussel; Evenset et al., 2009), and in Greenland shark (*Somniosus microcephalus*) liver from the Greenland Sea (Ademollo et al., 2018). Furthermore, chemicals with a lower octanol-water partition coefficient, like BPA and some phthalate metabolites like MEHP, may concentrate in marine mammal liver and may be nondetectable in blubber. As such, although a large number of unexpected chemicals were both tentatively identified and confirmed in the present study, further investigation using similar nontarget/suspect approaches with different library databases, in other marine mammal tissues (e.g., skin, muscle, liver), and using different analytical extraction methodologies is warranted, especially as some non-detected, yet toxic and persistent chemicals (or chemicals that were not screened) or their primary metabolites are still likely present.

These results may be further supported by future research using additional nontarget/suspect screening approaches including the use of more standards to confirm contaminant presence and quantify concentrations. Future work with additional chemical standards may be used to match retention time and MS/MS fragmentation patterns to those in the samples (Table 2) to identify and confirm, in particular, dioctyl sebacate, 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol, nonylphenol isomers, and other tentatively identified phthalates (e.g., dibutyl phthalate, benzyl butyl phthalate, and dibenzyl phthalate). Furthermore, as concentrations were only semi-quantified for a few compounds, follow-up analyses should detail concentrations by purchasing mass-labelled standards. In addition, different data treatment approaches, such as those provided by machine learning-based retention time predictions, could be employed to provide higher confidence of many tentatively-identified compounds in the present study, especially for more hydrophilic chemicals (Song et al., 2024). Nonetheless, previous studies using similar nontarget workflows were optimized and were shown to accurately identify chemicals in biological tissues (e.g., Tian et al., 2019); therefore, our high detection frequencies and comparison to legacy contaminants is likely sufficient to demonstrate never-before-seen PRC contamination in Arctic marine mammals and that further investigation into the presence of other PRCs and CEACs is warranted.

4. Conclusions

Here, we present the results of the first nontarget/suspect screening workflow specifically developed for the identification of novel and “unknown” contaminants in Arctic marine mammal toothed whales. Tentatively identifying 138 features, predominantly comprising of CEACs and PRCs, our comprehensive analysis compared retention time and MS/MS fragmentation patterns for ~50 compounds with available authentic standards. We successfully confirmed the presence of multiple PRCs, including three phthalates (DEP, DEHP, DPHP) and one antioxidant, Irganox 1010. Three additional PRCs, a nonylphenol, 2,6-di-*tert*-butylphenol, and dioctyl sebacate, exhibited MS/MS fragmentation patterns matching those in library databases. While the low detection frequencies of the identified phthalates suggest limited bioaccumulation

and even trophic dilution in Arctic marine mammals, the high detection frequencies of Irganox 1010 and limited information on its usage, toxicity, and environmental persistence indicate the need for further investigation into its environmental fate and uptake in marine wildlife. In addition, the presence of some alkylphenols, especially those with known endocrine disrupting potential (i.e., some nonylphenols) warrants prioritization in future research. As indicated by the large number of unknown or unexpected chemicals, both tentatively identified and confirmed in this study, our current understanding of contaminant exposure in marine mammal predators is likely incomplete. Therefore, further nontarget analyses are essential to better characterize the magnitude of CEAC contamination in Arctic marine food webs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Adam F. Pedersen: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Stéphane Bayen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Lan Liu:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Rune Dietz:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Christian Sonne:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Aqqu Rosing-Asvid:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Steven H. Ferguson:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Melissa A. McKinney:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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